

IMPROVING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF A SOLAR AIR HEATING COLLECTOR BY CONTROLLING AIR DRIVE FAN SPEED

Sharobiddinov Saydullo O'ktamjon o'g'li

Mamarasulov Qudratbek Shuhratbek o'g'li

Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute

"Alternative energy sources"

intern-teacher of the department.

Gmail: saydullosharobiddinov41@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

To increase the energy efficiency of the solar air heating collector, controlling the speed of the air drive fan can have a significant effect. By controlling the speed of the air drive fan, it is possible to control the flow of air entering the solar air heating collector in small ranges, increasing or decreasing the temperature of the air leaving the collector. Control of the speed of the air drive fan is carried out by means of an adjusting element in pulsed supply sources.

Keywords. Solar air heating collector, rectifier element, pulse width modulator.

To increase the energy efficiency of a solar air heating collector, controlling the speed of its air drive fan is also very effective. In this process, by controlling the speed of the air drive fan, it is possible to control the flow of air entering the solar air heating collector in small ranges, increasing or decreasing the temperature of the air leaving the collector. Control of the speed of the air drive fan is carried out by means of an adjusting element in pulsed supply sources.

Despite the many types of circuits of pulse power supplies, all of them are divided into two groups according to the control of the rectifier element: pulse-

width modulated (or frequency modulated) power supplies and relay-controlled power supplies through the rectifier element . The air drive fan is equipped with a small power permanent magnet DC motor. It is considered appropriate to use a Pulse Width Modulator to control its speed.

Figure 1. Pulse width modulator.

By controlling the speed of the solar air heating collector air drive fan through the pulse width modulator, we can control the temperature of the air leaving the solar air heating collector in small ranges by changing the flow of air entering and leaving the collector. By increasing the speed of the air drive fan, it is possible to reduce the temperature of the air leaving the solar air heating collector. It was observed that the air coming out of the solar air heating collector decreased by 1°C for every 208 times the fan rotation speed was increased. The table below shows the measurement results.

Figure 2. General view of the pulse width modulator installed on the solar air heating collector.

Air drive fan speed (rpm)	Temperature at the outlet of the collector (°C)
1250	39
1458	38
1666	37
1874	36
2082	35
2290	34
2500	33

Table 1. The air is obtained by increasing the rotation speed of the fan table of measurement results.

Figure 3. The graph of the dependence of the air temperature coming out of the collector on the speed of the fan.

As can be seen from the graph above, when the fan speed is increased to a maximum of 2500 rpm, the temperature of the air coming out of the solar air heating collector decreases by 6 °C. With this result, we can significantly control the air temperature in residential buildings or greenhouses with solar air heating collectors.

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